

Gate-to-gate life cycle assessment of lithium-ion battery recycling pre-treatment

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ABSTRACT

Recycling spent lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) is critical for enhancing environmental sustainability and resource conservation; however, the environmental and energy impacts of LIB recycling are not yet comprehensively understood due to the diverse applications of LIB cells and the variability in recycling technologies. This study presents a gate-to-gate life cycle assessment (LCA) of a recycling pre-treatment process at a small-scale plant in the Czech Republic, focusing on spent LIBs from electric vehicles (EVs) and consumer electronics cells (CECs). Using the SimaPro LCA software and the Ecoinvent 3.9 database, the analysis evaluated the environmental impact of recycling operations across several categories, including climate change, eutrophication, freshwater, and resource use, minerals and metals. The findings reveal that the recycling pre-treatment process for CECs achieves greater benefits in climate change mitigation compared to EV batteries relative to CECs. Moreover, the study highlights the effectiveness of optimized recycling practices in alleviating environmental burdens. A notable finding is the significance of secondary material recovery, particularly metals such as copper and aluminium, as these materials can substitute for primary raw materials, thereby minimizing resource use and reducing emissions. These aspects emphasize the need for high recovery efficiency to enhance environmental benefits. However, further research is essential to fully comprehend the environmental impacts of LIB recycling and to resolve uncertainties concerning battery composition and the effectiveness of different recycling technologies.

1. Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have become indispensable in modern technology due to their high energy density, lightweight design, and rechargeability. They power various devices, from portable consumer electronics to light or heavy means of transport, such as electric vehicles (EVs) or renewable energy storage systems (Kumar et al., 2023; Nitta et al., 2015; Sharma et al., 2020). The LIBs integration within transportation leads to a revolution in the automotive sector by providing a cleaner and more sustainable alternative to traditional internal combustion engines (Reddy et al., 2024; Ren et al., 2023). Vehicles equipped with LIBs offer reduced greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) and contribute to mitigating climate change (Jannesar Niri et al., 2024; Reddy et al., 2024). Nevertheless, the environmental benefit should be considered within the entire lifespan of the product, process, or activity (Ilgin and Gupta, 2010). This includes not only the manufacturing and use phases but also the disposal or end-of-life (EOL) stage (Klöpffer and Grahl,

2014).

Recycling holds significant benefits for both the environment and the economy (Kwade and Diekmann, 2018; Pražanová et al., 2022a, 2022b). Commonly used LIBs are rich in valuable metals in battery electrodes, such as cobalt, lithium, manganese, and nickel, and other essential metals and minerals, including aluminium, copper, graphite, or iron within the rest of battery components, such as battery collectors and casings (Ferg et al., 2019; Li et al., 2018; Pražanová et al., 2022a). Considering the still-rising demand within a wide range of their application fields, recycling LIBs is crucial for effective waste management. Moreover, recycling conservates virgin material sources, reduces the environmental impact associated with mining and extraction, such as the emissions of GHGs, and contributes to the circular economy by closing the loop on selected materials (Mossali et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2018). However, even the recycling processes are energy-intensive, generate emissions into water and air, and pose the risk of releasing toxic substances into the environment (Pražanová et al., 2022b; Zhang

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et al., 2018).

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is typically used to thoroughly quantify the environmental impacts of a product. LCA should ideally cover all stages of the product's life cycle, from raw material extraction to disposal ("cradle-to-grave"), but it can also focus on specific life cycle stages ("gate-to-gate") (Klöpper and Grahl, 2014). Evaluating specific life cycle phases is essential for understanding the complexity and impact of procedures. This assessment enables the identification of opportunities for further optimization, ultimately reducing the overall environmental impact of the monitored processes (Ilgin and Gupta, 2010; Klöpper and Grahl, 2014).

Very few LCAs addressing LIB recycling treatment have been documented in published literature. Moreover, the works vary significantly in their aims, scope, level of detail, assumed battery type, composition chemistry, and the employed assessment method. A comprehensive analysis of the impacts of recycling using cradle-to-gate LCA, focusing on energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions of automotive LIBs, was provided by Dunn et al. (2012). Their work covered the "closed loop" recycling by pyrometallurgy, hydrometallurgy, and direct physical separation of the lithium manganese oxide (LMO) cathode and current collector materials. According to their approach, the direct physical recycling of LMO, aluminium, and copper could reduce energy consumption during material production by up to 48%. A similar study was provided by Hendrickson et al. (2015), who dealt with closed-loop pyrometallurgical and hydrometallurgical processing of LMO. Their finding revealed that material recovery from pyrometallurgy can mitigate environmental impacts associated with LIB production via a 6–56% reduction in primary energy demand and a 23% reduction in GHG emissions compared to virgin production. Further, the assessment of Elwert et al. (2015) focused on hydrometallurgical recycling of nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) LIBs, highlighted the environmental benefits resulting from the recovery of the outer steel casing to a lesser degree, the cobalt and nickel present in the cathode materials. Rajaeifar et al. (2021) presented a comparative study of different pyrometallurgical techniques. In contrast, Cusenza et al., 2019 reported an evaluation of recycling an LMO-NMC LIB pack using a combination of pyrometallurgical and hydrometallurgical processes.

Despite the progress made, there is still a significant knowledge gap in the environmental assessment of the initial stage of recycling LIBs, referred to as recycling pre-treatment (Chan et al., 2020; Fujita et al., 2021; Pražanová et al., 2022a). This phase includes battery discharging, disassembly, crushing, rough material separation, and the removal of organic components through thermal treatment. The result of this process, known as black mass, is a finely ground mixture composed of various materials extracted from battery components, notably containing valuable metals (Kwade Arno & Diekmann Jan 2018). A recent study by Fridrich et al. (2024) provides a detailed gate-to-gate LCA of the recycling pre-treatment process for different types of LIBs, emphasizing the environmental impacts and significant recovery of secondary aluminium, and finding that variations in battery chemistry do not significantly affect the environmental impacts of these procedures.

This paper addresses a critical gap in the current understanding of LIB recycling by focusing on the pre-treatment phase, which has received limited attention in the literature. While most studies analyse the environmental impacts of the complete recycling process, the pre-treatment stage, which is crucial for material recovery and downstream process efficiency, has been underexplored. With the increasing adoption of LIBs, particularly in EVs and CECs, the demand for efficient and environmentally responsible recycling processes is more pressing than ever.

This study offers a detailed gate-to-gate LCA of pretreatment process in the case of a small-scale recycling plant in the Czech Republic, specifically examining the pre-treatment of LIBs from EVs and CECs. By analysing key environmental impact categories, such as climate change, eutrophication, freshwater use, and resource depletion, the paper highlights the considerable environmental benefits of optimizing the

pre-treatment process. To reflect market realities, the study selected representative battery types from both EVs and CECs. For EV batteries, the focus was on lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC), a leading chemistry in modern electric vehicles. For CECs, the analysis included lithium manganese oxide (LMO), lithium iron phosphate (LFP), and lithium nickel cobalt aluminium oxide (NCA) in equal proportions, capturing the diversity of battery chemistries used in consumer electronics. Given that pre-treatment is a necessary step in LIB recycling, as it enables the efficient recovery of valuable materials while meeting regulatory constraints (EUR-Lex, 2023; United States Environmental Protection Agency, 1976), a scenario without pre-treatment was not considered in this study. Alternative approaches, such as landfilling, are legally restricted in many regions (EUR-Lex, 2023), and direct incineration is not viable due to the economic value of recoverable metals like cobalt and nickel (Li et al., 2018). Consequently, this research focuses on evaluating and improving pre-treatment processes as they represent the only practical and sustainable pathway for EOL LIB management. The results show that recycling CECs yields a more substantial reduction in climate change impacts compared to the recycling of EV batteries. Additionally, the study identifies opportunities to improve resource efficiency and reduce emissions by enhancing pre-treatment practices, especially in small-scale facilities that serve as critical components of the LIB recycling network. At the same time, the recovery of critical metals like copper and aluminium plays a pivotal role in minimizing resource use and emissions. This research offers valuable insights into the environmental performance of LIB recycling and highlights the critical role of achieving high recovery efficiency to fully unlock these technologies' sustainability potential.

By refining existing methods and expanding the scope to include various battery types, the study contributes to the ongoing efforts to optimize recycling processes in response to growing global battery demand. Furthermore, the findings bridge a significant gap in the existing literature by focusing on the environmental performance of pre-treatment, offering a basis for future comparative studies and advancing the understanding of this critical stage in LIB recycling.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Goal, scope, and assumptions

LCA is a standardized method used to assess the environmental impacts of a product, process, or service throughout its life cycle, from raw material extraction to disposal (cradle-to-grave). Partial LCA studies, or "gate-to-gate" analyses, focus on specific life cycle stages to evaluate their impacts. This study performed a gate-to-gate LCA to assess the environmental impacts of the pre-treatment phase in LIB recycling (Klöpper and Grahl, 2014). The system boundary of this study is defined as encompassing the recycling pre-treatment processes of EOL LIBs from EVs and consumer CECs, covering five main steps: deep discharging, disassembly, crushing, separation, and thermal treatment. Inputs include EOL batteries, energy, and auxiliary materials, while outputs include recovered black mass, secondary materials (e.g., copper and aluminium), lost fractions, and hazardous waste such as wastewater. The detailed system boundary is illustrated in Fig. 1 (c). Moreover, it is assumed that using recycled materials avoids the environmental impacts associated with producing new materials, thus reflecting the benefits of avoided products. The functional unit for this assessment is defined as one metric tonne of recycled batteries, representing the amount of material processed through the pre-treatment phase. This choice ensures consistency with LCA best practices and facilitates direct comparison with similar studies in the literature. The selection of one metric tonne as the functional unit also aligns with industry norms and reflects a practical scale for evaluating the environmental performance of small-scale recycling facilities. Additionally, this approach captures the diversity of battery chemistries processed and their respective contributions to environmental impacts, as detailed in the system boundaries.

Fig. 1. (a) Process scheme of the recycling pre-treatment steps for spent lithium-ion batteries from electric vehicles and consumer electronics; (b) energy mix composition for analysed scenarios in 2022 and 2030 (CEPS, 2021); (c) end-of-life (EOL) phase of lithium-ion battery life cycle with a system boundaries highlighted in red, related to gate-to-gate life cycle analysis of recycling pre-treatment.

The study presents a case study of a recycling plant in central Europe, specifically in the Czech Republic, which is dedicated to the recycling pre-treatment of spent LIB systems from EVs and consumer CECs. This evaluation is focused on study case scenarios grounded in established best practices, extensive experience in the field, relevant literature, and informed estimates based on existing research and data. The scope explicitly excludes downstream processes, such as refining of recovered black mass or reuse of electrolyte residues. A schematic illustration of the five-step recycling pre-treatment process studied in this work, including the characterized process inputs (EOL batteries) and outputs, such as reused, not treated, secondary and lost materials, is presented in Fig. 1 (a). Fig. 1 (c) provides a detailed depiction of the system boundaries, clearly delineating the cradle-to-gate processes included in this analysis. Detailed information on consumption and individual quantities is provided in Supplementary Materials (SM).

The whole process starts with a deep discharge step, which is essential for further safe and promising processing (Liu et al., 2022; Pražanová et al., 2022a). For EV technology, the electric active discharging procedures are typically preferred (Kwade Arno & Diekmann Jan 2018). Thus, for the case of EV battery systems (packs), a suitable battery discharge system with reduced energy consumption and high efficiency with a recovery energy capability of up to 96% is used (Keysight, 2024). The discharge process is included within the system boundary and contributes to annual energy consumption of 19.2 MWh. Within the CECs treatment, electrochemical discharge in 10 wt % sodium chloride (NaCl) and water solution, as the favourable discharging procedure, is applied (Ojanen et al., 2018; Rouhi et al., 2021). Discharging is conducted under strict safety protocols, including the ventilation of toxic fumes and continuous monitoring (Kong et al., 2018; Work Australia, 2012). The discharge bath, with a total volume of 2.5 m³, is filtered as part of the operation and reused throughout the year.

The battery packs are manually disassembled using only small power tools at the battery module level due to the high complexity and wide variety of treated systems (An, 2019). This disassembly stage is part of the defined system boundary, with manual labour and power tools representing the primary resource consumption. The next step involves crushing either battery cells or entire battery units, facilitating the separation of their materials (Kwade Arno & Diekmann Jan 2018; Pražanová et al., 2022a). The modules are subsequently crushed in a two-step procedure using a double-shaft rubber recycling crusher and a rotor impact mill (Kwade Arno & Diekmann Jan 2018). The system boundary includes emissions of volatile solvents or particulate matter during this stage (Kwade Arno & Diekmann Jan 2018), which are captured by ventilation systems but not further processed within this analysis. The scope of this study does not cover their more detailed processing or reusing. Crushing CECs is done likewise. During the electrochemical discharging, volatile solvents and electrolyte are released into the solution (Pražanová et al., 2023). The subsequent disposal of this wastewater as hazardous waste (He et al., 2024; Mondal et al., 2024), along with its energy and resource demands, falls within the system boundary. The treated cells are rinsed with water and crushed using the same process steps as in the EV route. The final product of this line is black mass, i.e., a finely ground mix of fractions of battery components (Kwade Arno & Diekmann Jan 2018), which has been treated with selected processes (separation and thermal treatment) to remove plastics, binders, conductive additives, electrolyte residues, or other materials such as current collector metals (copper and aluminium), graphite from anode layers or casing materials (iron and steel). Outputs from this stage, such as black mass, metals, and other recyclable fractions, represent the final outputs within the system boundary. The study does not include further downstream processing of these outputs. More detailed information on the individual processes can be found within the SM.

The assessment was conducted for a case study of a small-scaled pilot recycling line, explicitly defining the system boundary to focus on pre-treatment operations, including discharging, disassembly, and

crushing processes, but excluding downstream processing steps such as hydrometallurgical or pyrometallurgical recycling. The pilot line handles approximately one-third of the processing capacity compared to the current operations in central Europe (Baum et al., 2022). Thus, a single-shift operation (8 working hours) for 252 days per year, reflecting realistic conditions for small-scale facilities, was considered. The processing of EV battery systems and CECs in the recycling plant was assumed to occur in separate production cycles and is not done simultaneously. For clarity, the operational schedule was divided as follows: EV battery packs are processed for 240 days annually, while CECs are processed once a month for 12 days.

For EV battery systems, each battery pack was assumed to weigh between 400 and 420 kg, with 5 systems processed per shift, resulting in a total annual processing capacity of 500 tonnes. For CECs, a different processing approach was applied: 4 tonnes of batteries per shift were processed, resulting in a total annual capacity of 48 tonnes. To better contextualize the study, the EV battery systems processed in the pilot line were assumed to predominantly consist of lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) technology. This reflects one of the leading chemical compositions of EV LIBs today. In contrast, the CEC processing line was considered to handle batteries based on lithium manganese oxide (LMO), lithium iron phosphate (LFP), and lithium nickel cobalt aluminium oxide (NCA), all in equal proportions (16 tonnes of each type annually). Material proportions and the mass of individual battery components were detailed to enhance traceability and provided in Table 1 for reference.

In the assessed case, the recycling hall of the plant spans an area of 200 m², complemented by a 100 m² battery warehouse. The evaluation encompasses energy consumption for heating, air conditioning, security monitoring, and additional ventilation during electrochemical discharge or battery unit crushing. The SM provide detailed information regarding the energy consumption of individual recycling preparation or revision processes, totalling 0.18 GWh/year of plant operation.

2.2. Evaluated scenario and sensitivity analysis

This study evaluates the plant's operation dedicated to recycling pre-treatment of spent LIBs in their EV battery packs, and CECs type was conducted based on an implementation scenario (Scenario 2022), which utilizes the average energy mix data of the Czech Republic for 2022. This year was selected due to data availability, as only complete data for 2022 were accessible when the study began in early 2023. Additionally, to illustrate the impact of changes in the energy mix composition over time, Scenario 2022 was compared to the predicted energy mix composition for 2030 (Scenario 2030). The year 2030 was chosen based on projections indicating a transition towards a greener energy mix, including a reduction in coal reliance and an increase in renewables such as solar power. The composition of the energy mix in 2022 relied on data from the Czech electricity and gas market operator (OTE) database (OTE, 2024). Predictions for the 2030 energy mix were drawn from the "Resource Adequacy Assessment of the Electrical Grid of the Czech Republic until 2040" (MAF CZ 2022) (ČEPS, 2021). The composition of considered energy mixes is shown in Fig. 1 (b).

Both case studies assumed ~100% efficiency for the recycling technology and a ~100% share of secondary use for the obtained materials. While these assumptions represent an idealized scenario based on optimistic projections, they may not fully reflect the recovery and separation rates achievable with existing technologies. The materials were separated with ~100% efficiency, ensuring the resulting black mass achieved the highest possible quality. This demonstrates a highly optimistic scenario, intended to evaluate the maximum potential environmental benefits of recycling. Such a scenario is valuable as it highlights the upper bound of potential environmental gains, providing a benchmark for future improvements and showing what can be accomplished under ideal conditions. However, it is important to note that real-world operations with lower efficiency may result in reduced

Table 1

The material proportion and mass of treated lithium-ion battery components (Baazouzi et al., 2023; Deshwal et al., 2022; Pražanová et al., 2022a; Sobianowska-Turek et al., 2021). The mass of cathode active materials corresponds to the maximal amounts of possibly obtained black mass in its highest quality.

Cell type Battery component	EV cells		Consumer electronics cells (CECs)						
	NMC wt. %	Total (tonnes)	LMO		LFP		NCA		Total (tonnes)
			wt. %	Total (tonnes)	wt. %	Total (tonnes)	wt. %	total (tonnes)	
Cathode	40	200	24	3.84	28	4.48	25	4.00	12.32
Al foils	15	75	17	2.72	19	3.04	15	2.40	8.16
Active materials	25	125	7	1.12	9	1.44	10	1.60	4.16
Anode	24	120	16	2.56	19	3.04	17	2.72	8.32
Cu foils	12	60	8	1.28	9	1.44	8	1.28	4.00
Graphite	12	60	8	1.28	10	1.6	9	1.44	4.32
Plastics	5	25	5	0.80	5	0.8	5	0.80	2.40
Metals	14	70	15	2.40	13	2.08	14	2.24	6.72
Binders	7	35	4	0.64	2	0.32	4	0.64	1.60
Electrolyte	10	50	36	5.76	33	5.28	35	5.60	16.64
Total	100	500	100	16	100	16	100	16	48

Note: EV – “Electric vehicle”; NMC – “Lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide”; LMO – “Lithium manganese oxide”; LFP – “Lithium iron phosphate”; NCA – “Lithium nickel cobalt aluminium oxide”.

environmental benefits compared to those presented in this study. Sensitivity analyses were conducted to account for these variations. Detailed quantities of the output materials are provided in Table 1. However, the limitation of this work is that the utilized data in Table 1 are based solely on previous literature, rather than directly collected from the field, due to either the unavailability of field data or their confidentiality. Furthermore, the potential for secondary use was maximized, aligning with the primary objective of recycling. In sensitivity analyses, materials not obtained as secondary materials (and whose environmental impacts are excluded from the system) represent the Cut-Off modelling approach.

The modelling approach defines avoided products as items prevented from coming into existence through specific interventions. In our system, secondary materials are treated as avoided products, often associated with negative environmental impacts, as their use offsets the production of new materials. This approach accounts for the environmental burdens these secondary materials help mitigate. Sensitivity analysis 1 (SA1) is dedicated to Scenario 2022 and describes the effects of the implemented technology efficiency, which directly impacts the quality of the obtained materials. The efficiency is influenced by the applied recycling methods and their ability to recover specific material categories, as listed in Table 2. For instance, the recovery of electrolyte is

Table 2

The assumptions used in the sensitivity analyses (SA) for evaluating the recycling pre-treatment scenarios of spent lithium-ion batteries.

Sensitivity analysis parameter	Material category	SA1 variants (based on Scenario 2022)				
		A	B	C	D	Scenario 2022
Technology efficiency	Electrolyte	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
	Plastics, binders	0%				
	Graphite		0%			
	Other	80%	80%	80%		
	Metals Al & Cu foils				80%	
Sensitivity analysis parameter	Material category	SA2 variants (based on Scenario 2022)				
		X	Y	Z	Scenario 2022	
Secondary usage	Electrolyte	0%	0%	50%	100%	
	Plastics, binders					
	Graphite					
	Other Metals			100%		
	Al & Cu foils					

assumed to be 100%, while graphite recovery is considered 0% in variants A, B, and C. In variant D, the recovery efficiency of all materials is set to match the baseline Scenario 2022. These variants simulate the effect of technology improvements or degradations on recovery rates and highlight their influence on environmental outcomes. In this case, a ~100% secondary use of the recovered materials was assumed. The efficiency of the process is determined by the percentage of obtained materials, according to their materials type, including electrolyte, plastics, binders, graphite, other metals, and Al & Cu foils within the material flows of the recycling pre-treatment operation, as illustrated in Table 2. While a ~100% recovery rate was assumed for modelling purposes, real-world recovery rates for certain materials may be lower, which could affect the environmental benefit results. Detailed data are provided in SM.

Sensitivity analysis 2 (SA2) is focused on assessing the secondary use effect in Scenario (2022). This analysis evaluates scenarios X, Y, and Z to explore the extent to which secondary material usage influences environmental outcomes. Variant X assumes no secondary use, meaning all materials are directed to landfills or incineration, while variant Y assumes partial secondary use (e.g., 50% for graphite). Variant Z assumes full secondary use of recovered materials, aligning with Scenario 2022. These variations test the dependency of environmental benefits on secondary material applications. The evaluation considers the highest quality black mass product (achieved through ~100% efficiency of the implemented technology), and the secondary usage shares for selected material groups are shown in Table 2.

In an ideal scenario, materials such as Al and copper Cu foils, metals, graphite, and plastics are considered secondary materials, which can be recycled and reused. However, electrolytes are typically only partially treated through wastewater or incinerated in kilns. Binders, on the other hand, are always directed to landfills. Furthermore, if secondary materials are not recycled, they end up in landfills. Within the provided sensitivity analysis, the scenarios are highly optimistic, demonstrating the maximum possible environmental benefits from recycling that can be achieved within the considered processes. Such an optimistic outlook underscores the potential for significant environmental improvements and serves as a guide for maximizing the efficiency of future recycling technologies. While the energy mix used to power the recycling pre-treatment line improves in time (emissions get lower), the environmental footprint of avoided products stays the same. This leads to a higher positive impact of battery recycling on the environment. The input data of this evaluation are given in SM.

2.3. Life cycle assessment approach

This study provides a partial gate-to-gate LCA for the selected

recycling pre-treatment processes for spent LIBs, conducted via the 9.5.0.0 version of SimaPro LCA modeling software using the Ecoinvent 3.9. database with a Cut-Off approach and Environmental Footprint 3.1 (EF 3.1) life cycle impact assessment method (European Platform on LCA | EPLCA, 2024). The system boundaries focus on the pre-treatment phase, covering all processes required to discharge, dismantle, and shred the batteries into fractions suitable for downstream recovery. Processes related to collection, transportation, and final material recovery (recycling) are excluded, as they fall outside the scope of this study. The functional unit for the analysis is defined as one metric tonne of spent LIBs processed through the pre-treatment phase, ensuring comparability with similar studies and practical relevance to the recycling industry. The scope of this study and system boundaries within the whole LIB life cycle are highlighted in red and shown in Fig. 1 (c). The processes from the Ecoinvent database used for LCA modeling are presented in Table 3. Each process was carefully selected to align with the defined system boundaries and to ensure consistency in representing the material flows, energy inputs, and emissions specific to the studied facility. These processes were carefully selected to provide a foundation for the analysis and were subsequently transformed and modified based on the available inventory data to better align with the specific conditions of the study, ensuring that the modeling reflects the most accurate and relevant environmental impacts.

Environmental impact categories (EICs) can vary depending on the context of the assessment and the specific goals of the study (EF3.1 Impact Categories | Earthster Knowledge Base, 2024). Commonly recognized EICs include climate change, resource depletion, water pollution, air pollution, ecotoxicity, land use, and waste generation. For this study, three main EICs were identified: climate change, eutrophication, and resource use (specifically minerals and metals). These categories were selected based on their relevance to the environmental performance of LIB pre-treatment processes and their alignment with key regulatory and industrial priorities. To enhance the reliability of results, normalization and sensitivity analyses were conducted, ensuring that the selected categories adequately capture the critical environmental impacts of the studied system. Chosen categories were based on normalized results (Klöpper and Grahl, 2014).

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) characterization model is used to evaluate the impacts of climate change. This model provides characterization factors quantified as the Global Warming Potential over a 100-year time frame (GWP100), expressed in kilograms of carbon dioxide equivalent (kg CO₂ eq.) per kilogram of emission. The indicator operates on a global scale. The GWP data reported by the IPCC are specifically related to emissions to the air. To align these values with the classifications used in the ILCD (International

Life Cycle Data system) and EF (Environmental Footprint) frameworks, they have been distributed across various emission compartments, including emissions to the lower stratosphere and upper troposphere, emissions to non-urban air or from high stacks, and emissions to urban air close to the ground (Glasson and Therivel; Klöpper and Grahl, 2014; Myhre G. et al., 2013).

Eutrophication, freshwater EIC measures the degree to which freshwater ecosystems become overly enriched with nutrients, stemming from emissions of compounds containing phosphorus. This process encompasses all effects linked to the excessive presence of macronutrients in the environment, originating from nutrient emissions to air, water, and soil. Additionally, it represents the expression of the degree to which the emitted nutrients reach the freshwater end compartment (phosphorus is considered a limiting factor in freshwater) (Struijs et al., 2009).

Resource use, minerals and metals EIC focuses on the consumption of natural non-fossil resources, specifically minerals and metals. The indicator is associated with the extraction of minerals and fossil fuels as inputs into various systems. The Abiotic Depletion Factor (ADF) calculates the impact of each mineral extraction, expressed in kilograms of antimony equivalents (Sb eq.), considering reserve concentrations and the rate of depletion. This indicator's applicability is global, encompassing the entire planet (Glasson & Therivel, n.d.; Klöpper and Grahl, 2014; Van Oers et al., 2016).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Scenario 2022; 2030 comparison

The comprehensive assessment of this study involved calculating the annual environmental impacts for selected operational scenarios and comparing the impacts based on the energy mixes for 2022 and 2030. A summary of these impacts is provided in the SM. The results highlight that the recycling pre-treatment of spent LIBs has environmental benefits (negative sign of the environmental impacts) due to assumption that the recycled materials replace production of virgin materials, which environmental impacts are deducted. This approach is commonly applied in LCA under the concept of avoided products (the production of virgin materials is avoided due to recycled materials). Fig. 2 illustrates the comparison of case study scenarios modelled with different energy mixes for 2022 and 2030.

The comparison indicates that recycling EV batteries results in higher environmental benefits for eutrophication, freshwater use, and resource use (including minerals and metals) compared to CECs. However, CECs offer higher environmental benefits for climate change than

Table 3

The inventory of Ecoinvent 3.9 processes used for the life cycle analysis modelling.

Ecovinent 3.9 processes
<i>Secondary materials (their production is considered as avoided product by materials recycled during pre-treatment process)</i>
Polypropylene, granulate {RER} polypropylene production, granulate Cut-off, U
Polyethylene, high density, granulate {RER} polyethylene production, high density, granulate Cut-off, U
Pig iron {RER} pig iron production Cut-off, U
Aluminium, primary, ingot {RoW} aluminium production, primary, ingot Cut-off, U
Copper, cathode {GLO} market for copper, cathode Cut-off, U
Synthetic graphite, battery grade {RoW} synthetic graphite production, battery grade Cut-off, U
<i>Waste products</i>
Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U
Sewage sludge, 75% water, WWT, WW, average {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of sewage sludge, 75% water, WWT, WW, average, sanitary landfill Cut-off, U
Waste plastic plaster, for final disposal {RoW} treatment of waste plastic plaster, inert material landfill Cut-off, U
<i>Other (machines, energy)</i>
Industrial machine, heavy, unspecified {RER} market for industrial machine, heavy, unspecified Cut-off, U
Salt {GLO} market for salt Cut-off, U
Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} tap water production, conventional treatment Cut-off, U
Conveyor belt {RER} conveyor belt production Cut-off, U
Electricity, low voltage {CZ} electricity voltage transformation from medium to low voltage Cut-off, U
Auxiliary heating unit, electric, 5 kW {GLO} market for auxiliary heating unit, electric, 5 kW Cut-off, U

Note: RER – “Rest of Europe”; RoW – “Rest of the world”; GLO – “Global”; WWT – “Wastewater treatment”; WW – “Wastewater”; CZ – “Czech Republic”.

Fig. 2. Comparison of scenarios regarding energy mix compositions in 2022 and 2030, illustrating selected environmental impact categories: (a) climate change, (b) eutrophication, freshwater, and (c) resource use, minerals and metals. Results are presented per functional unit of one metric tonne of end-of-life lithium-ion batteries.

EV batteries. Specifically, this is attributed to the lower energy intensity of processing CEC batteries and the differences in avoided products derived from their material composition. Using the 2022 energy mix, CECs demonstrate environmental benefits of 80% in eutrophication, freshwater, and 69% in resource use, minerals, and metals relative to EV batteries. In contrast, EV batteries have 5% lower benefits for climate change compared to CECs.

The differences in resource use, minerals and metals EIC between CECs and EV cells arise mainly from variations in the internal material ratios, such as cathode active materials. For example, EV batteries often rely on cobalt- and nickel-rich cathodes (e.g., NMC), which significantly contribute to resource depletion metrics, while CECs commonly use materials with lower criticality, such as manganese-based cathodes (e.g., LMO). These differences are key contributors to the environmental impacts observed in LIB recycling. Proper processing of CECs is crucial for environmental sustainability, highlighting the importance of addressing CEC waste in recycling pre-treatment efforts.

Additionally, despite variations in energy mixes, the production technology of avoided products (such as Al and Cu) remains constant across the scenarios. This assumption reflects the current state of metallurgical recovery technologies and their efficiency, which are assumed not to change significantly in the short term. The comparison reveals that the energy mix significantly affects eutrophication and freshwater EICs (>20%), has a moderate impact on climate change EIC (<17%), and a minimal effect on resource use, minerals, and metals EIC (<1%). These results underline the role of energy transition in shaping the environmental benefits of recycling technologies, particularly for impact categories sensitive to energy sources.

Overall, the 2030 scenario shows a substantial improvement in environmental benefits for the first two categories, mainly due to the reduced reliance on coal-fired power plants, which constituted nearly half of the Czech Republic's energy mix in 2022 but is expected to drop to less than a third by 2030. This improvement underscores the importance of aligning recycling strategies with cleaner energy systems to maximize environmental performance. In contrast, the benefits related to resource use, minerals, and metals EIC show a decline, with only a marginal change of 0.20% observed in comparison to treated battery cell technologies.

3.1.1. A detailed breakdown within Scenario 2022

To offer a comprehensive understanding of the influence and characteristics of the output product, a detailed breakdown was created for Scenario 2022, as shown in Fig. 3. This breakdown includes the processing of output materials across various impact categories: recycling line, waste binders, electrolyte (including electricity used in plant

operations), wastewater treatment, and secondary plastics, secondary iron and steel, secondary aluminium, secondary copper, and secondary graphite. These categories were selected based on their relevance to the key environmental impacts associated with the recycling process, as well as their contribution to the material recovery system. The impacts of these categories and their total contributions to the selected EICs were analysed and determined.

The analysed EICs reflect the environmental impact of further processing of materials within the output flows. For disposal-related categories, such as recycling line, waste binders, electrolyte, and wastewater treatment, environmental impacts were assessed across all categories. This is largely a result of the Czech energy mix, where over 40% derived from fossil fuels, powering the recycling process. This underscores the critical role of energy sources in shaping the environmental outcomes of recycling activities, highlighting the importance of integrating cleaner energy alternatives into future recycling technologies. In contrast, the reuse of materials, represented by the “secondary” categories, results in negative values for environmental impacts, thus reducing overall impacts and providing environmental benefits. Such benefits assume that secondary materials, once recovered, displace the need for primary extraction and production processes, leading to a reduction in environmental impacts across multiple categories. Wastewater processing was not considered in the context of EV battery unit treatment in this study, leading to zero impact in all selected EICs. However, the exclusion of wastewater treatment should be acknowledged as a limitation in the assessment of water-related impacts. Details of the pre-treatment steps are illustrated in Fig. 1(a).

The categories “secondary copper” and “secondary aluminium” significantly impact the analysis because their use in place of primary production leads to the deduction of potential environmental impacts, thanks to the assumed 100% recovery rate for these metals. While aluminium's impact on the resource use, minerals, and metals EIC is minimal due to its abundance, its high-energy production process has a major effect on climate change. This highlights the trade-off between the resource availability of a material and the energy required for its recovery. Conversely, copper has a more substantial impact on metal depletion. Given its limited natural reserves and high demand in industries beyond batteries, copper recovery plays a key role in reducing metal depletion. The environmental benefits of recovering secondary plastic parts, steel, and iron from consumer electronics cells and electric vehicle cells are comparable, as both types of battery cells contain similar proportions of these materials. However, the benefits of recovering these materials are contingent on the processing efficiency and the quality of the recycling technologies employed.

Fig. 3. A detailed breakdown of environmental impact categories within Scenario 2022, a) climate change, b) eutrophication, freshwater, and c) resource use, minerals and metals.

3.2. Sensitivity analysis

Two sensitivity analyses are provided in this study. SA1 examines the impact of technology efficiency, while SA2 focuses on the effect of secondary material usage on selected EICs. The results are organized by battery cell type, with EV cells shown in Figure (a) and CECs in Figure (b). Variants are listed alphabetically and arranged from least to most efficient in terms of technology or secondary material usage. The variant demonstrating the greatest environmental benefit, marked by the most negative EIC value, is considered the baseline at 100%. All

other variants are evaluated relative to this baseline to determine their impact and changes. Additional details are available in Table 2.

3.2.1. Technology efficiency impact

The impacts of all monitored EICs for both battery technologies are contingent upon the effectiveness of the technology employed. As technology efficiency improves, the potential for mitigating environmental impacts increases, highlighting the crucial role of process optimization. All analysed scenarios lead to negative impacts; nevertheless, as the efficiency of the technology decreases, so does the ability to

reduce or mitigate environmental impacts. The results of SA1 are illustrated in detail in Fig. 4.

Analysing both battery types reveals differences in EIC changes as technology efficiencies vary. For both EV batteries and CECs, differences between variants C and D were negligible (up to 2%) due to a 20% increase in efficiency for the recycling of other metals from 80% to 100%. The most significant changes occurred when the recycling efficiency for Al and Cu foils increased to 100%. Significant improvements were noted when the recycling efficiency of high-impact materials such as Al and Cu foils was optimized. In comparing variant D to the “energy mix 2022” scenario, substantial improvements were observed, with reductions in EICs ranging from 20% to 25% for climate change, eutrophication, freshwater, and resource use, minerals and metals. For CECs, the reductions were similarly substantial.

The difference between variants A and B, involving the processing of plastics and binders, was minimal across both battery types, particularly for CECs. The difference in resource use, minerals, and metals EIC is negligible, as the impact of plastics and binders on this category is limited. Even with a 100% increase in processing efficiency for these materials, the change in overall EICs remains modest, with the greatest reductions observed in climate change impacts. Climate change impacts showing a range of approximately 3–8% for EVs and negligible effects

(up to 2%) on other categories for CECs. In both pre-treatment recycling pathways, notable differences were found between variants B and C when graphite processing efficiency increased to 100%. This led to 6–8% changes in climate change and negligible impacts (up to 2%) for eutrophication, freshwater, and resource use, minerals and metals in EV cells and CECs recycling route.

The SA1 results emphasize that nearly all materials are either recycled or landfilled, demonstrating the benefits of effective secondary treatment in LIB recycling for EICs, especially climate change, eutrophication, freshwater and resource use, minerals and metals. The efficiency of Al and Cu foil recovery plays a pivotal role in achieving the largest environmental benefits. At the same time, changes in the recycling efficiency of plastics and binders have had a negligible effect on all monitored EICs.

3.1.2. Secondary material usage impact

The SA2 results highlight the critical role of secondary material used in recycling pre-treatment, significantly affecting environmental impacts, as shown in Fig. 5. The most negligible differences between variants Y and the “energy mix 2022” scenario were observed for both EV cells and CECs, comparing 100% secondary use with complete recycling. For EV cells, the differences were negligible (up to 2%) for climate

Fig. 4. Sensitivity analysis 1 results describing the effect of efficiency of implemented technology for (a) consumer electronics cells and (b) electric vehicle cells. Presented results reflect the standardized comparison with the assistance of a functional unit (one metric tonne of end-of-life lithium-ion batteries).

Fig. 5. Sensitivity analysis 2 results address the effect of the secondary material impact usage for (a) consumer electronics cells and (b) electric vehicle cells. Presented results reflect the standardized comparison with the assistance of a functional unit (one metric tonne of end-of-life lithium-ion batteries).

change, and eutrophication, freshwater impacts, while the resource use, minerals and metals impact was around 0.2%. For CECs, the differences were similarly minimal, with negligible changes for climate change and eutrophication, freshwater and approximately 0.2% for resource use, minerals and metals.

Variant Z, involving 50% material reuse, shows moderate reductions in environmental impacts compared to complete processing with “energy mix 2022.” For EV cells, reductions are about 67% for both climate change, and eutrophication, freshwater, and around 50% for resource use, minerals, and metals. For CECs, the reductions are similarly significant, with approximately 64% for climate change and around 50% for resource use, minerals and metals.

In contrast, variant X, with no secondary processing, worsens impacts across all categories, emphasizing the importance of secondary material use. Without secondary processing, the environmental benefits of recycling are severely diminished. For both battery types, the rise in the resource use impact category is minimal; however, the increase in climate change is notable. For EVs, the impact rises from -3700 kg CO₂ eq. to 1300 kg CO₂ eq., and for CECs, it increases from -3900 kg CO₂ eq. to 1100 kg CO₂ eq. Similarly, eutrophication and freshwater impacts increase: for EVs, from -5.5 kg CO₂ eq. to 1.9 kg CO₂ eq., and for CECs, from -4.4 kg CO₂ eq. to 1.5 kg CO₂ eq. These findings underscore the essential role of secondary metal use in achieving significant environmental benefits. Without it, the overall advantages of recycling are

severely diminished.

3.2.3. Sensitivity analysis results

When comparing the results from both the SA1 and SA2 analyses, it becomes clear that secondary material use is a crucial factor in the recycling and waste treatment of LIBs, regardless of whether the batteries are EV cells or CECs. Even with low-efficiency technology, characterized by poor material separation and reduced yield, the 100% reuse of recovered materials still led to environmentally favourable outcomes, reducing the impact of individual EICs by 17%–64%. This highlights the importance of optimizing material recovery processes and demonstrates that effective secondary material utilization is a key strategy for improving environmental performance, even under suboptimal technological conditions.

Conversely, even when using high-quality technology capable of recovering up to 100% of battery materials, neglecting the secondary use of these materials can still result in significant environmental impacts. For example, the “energy efficiency 2022” variant demonstrates that failing to reuse recovered materials can increase environmental impacts by as much as 35%. This finding underscores the importance of implementing comprehensive material recovery strategies, where not only the technological efficiency but also the post-recovery utilization phase plays a pivotal role in determining the overall environmental benefits.

The most significant benefits from secondary metal recovery are observed in the climate change impact category, primarily due to the high energy requirements of primary metal production. However, consistent achievement of high recovery rates is contingent upon advancements in both technology and economic feasibility, as not all facilities are equipped to employ the most efficient methods. Technological improvements in material separation, coupled with economic incentives for secondary material use, are essential for further enhancing the environmental sustainability of LIB recycling.

4. Conclusion

This study presents a comprehensive gate-to-gate LCA of LIB recycling pre-treatment at a small-scale facility in the Czech Republic, targeting EVs and CECs. The results are highly relevant for policymakers, recycling facility operators, and researchers focused on sustainable energy and material recovery. The findings highlight significant environmental benefits, particularly in reducing impacts on climate change, eutrophication, freshwater, resource use, minerals and metals. Notably, CEC recycling demonstrates greater effectiveness in climate change mitigation than EV battery recycling. This observation underscores the importance of developing tailored strategies for different battery types to optimize their recycling processes and maximize environmental benefits.

A key takeaway is the critical role of secondary material recovery, especially for metals like copper and aluminium, which substantially reduce resource use and emissions. Achieving high recovery efficiency is essential not only for material conservation but also for minimizing environmental impacts across multiple impact categories. To this end, recycling facilities must optimize technological processes to enhance material recovery and minimize environmental impacts.

To better contextualize the significance of the recycling pre-treatment, the environmental benefits were compared to the impacts associated with the production of batteries. In the climate change impact category, recycling results in a 35% reduction in environmental impact for CECs and 33% for EV batteries relative to their production impacts. In the eutrophication, freshwater category, recycling pre-treatment achieves a 45% reduction for CECs and 55% for EV batteries. Regarding resource use, minerals and metals, the environmental benefits of recycling are 38% for CECs and 55% for EV batteries. These findings highlight that the environmental advantages of recycling pre-treatment significantly outweigh the impacts of battery production. Consequently, LCA studies of technologies utilizing batteries that do not account for their recycling at the end of life may greatly exaggerate the environmental impacts of these technologies.

The analysis further highlights the critical role of a cleaner energy mix in reducing environmental impacts. As the energy grid transitions to lower-carbon sources, reductions in impacts, particularly eutrophication and freshwater use, are expected. This indicates that policy-driven transitions in the energy mix will further optimize LIB recycling processes, especially in terms of their environmental benefits. However, regardless of the energy scenario, efficient secondary material recovery remains indispensable to achieving optimal environmental outcomes.

While this study emphasizes the advantages of current pre-treatment methods, uncertainties regarding battery composition and the variable performance of recycling technologies remain. Expanding the data set to include a broader range of LIB chemistries and recycling methods would provide a more robust understanding of environmental impacts. A thorough assessment of specific recycling technologies, including pyrometallurgical, hydrometallurgical, and direct physical separation methods, would provide valuable insights into process efficiencies and environmental trade-offs. Furthermore, this study fills a notable gap in the literature by focusing on the pre-treatment phase, a critical yet often overlooked component of the LIB recycling process. The insights gained from this research establish a foundation for further comparative studies, providing an essential step towards more sustainable recycling

practices.

In conclusion, this study offers critical insights into optimizing LIB recycling processes, establishing a framework for enhancing recycling technologies and maximizing material recovery. Future research should aim to address existing data gaps and broaden LCA coverage to include a diverse array of battery chemistries and recycling pathways. Expanding the scope of future research will not only deepen our understanding of the pre-treatment process but also help optimize recycling strategies for a broader range of battery technologies, contributing to more sustainable energy transitions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Anna Pražanová: Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Michael Fridrich:** Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jan Weinzettel:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Vaclav Knap:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Anna Pražanová reports financial support was provided by Czech Technical University in Prague. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cesys.2025.100263>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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